

EXPLORING SOCIO-SCIENTIFIC REASONING SKILLS AMONG GRADE 11 STUDENTS

Kennedy G. Agapito, Jessie E. Quesea PhD

Science Department , Sacred Heart College of Lucena Inc, Lucena City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16026318>

ABSTRACT

Assessing the socio-scientific reasoning skills of Grade 11 students is crucial in understanding their ability to critically evaluate complex issues, consider diverse viewpoints, engage in thoughtful inquiry, and approach information with a questioning mindset. This study seeks to provide meaningful insights into their cognitive and analytical capabilities, aiding educators in developing more effective strategies to foster critical thinking and informed decision-making. Additionally, it examines the extent of socio-scientific reasoning skills in terms of complexity, perspective-taking, inquiry, and skepticism, while also identifying key influencing factors such as content acquisition, epistemology, and moral ethics. Finally, the study explores the potential correlation between these skills and the factors that shape their development. The study employed a descriptive survey and descriptive types of research and involved 236 grade 11 participants. Based on the results, the students have high-level socio-scientific reasoning skills in terms of complexity in understanding socio-scientific issues among the other variables. The students believe scientific knowledge is the driving force behind utilizing their socio-scientific reasoning skills to solve societal problems fully. Students used scientific information to solve socio-scientific matters, but some found it difficult to change their beliefs even when strong evidence was shown. The findings revealed no significant relationship between inquiry and any factors of socio-scientific reasoning skills. Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that administrators can design projects and programs that can enhance the socio-scientific reasoning skills of the students. The teachers can disseminate the output of this study to the students to measure and determine the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills. The school can use

the study results to enhance the teaching strategies and utilize the socio-scientific issues in the curriculum as essential to fully engaging students in solving societal problems.

Keywords: *Socio-scientific reasoning, Complexity, Perspective-taking, Inquiry, Skepticism*

INTRODUCTION

Science education equips learners with the knowledge and skills to develop scientific and technological literacy. Its key objective is to nurture scientifically literate individuals who not only possess a firm grasp of scientific concepts but are also capable of making well-informed decisions regarding various issues (Badeo & Duque, 2022). On the other hand, socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) plays a vital role in encompassing students' capacity to engage with socio-scientific issues (SSI), including four dimensions: complexity, perspective-taking, inquiry, and skepticism. They require evidence-based reasoning and critical evaluation to address their multifaceted nature. It represents complex societal dilemmas characterized by the absence of straightforward solutions and a strong connection to scientific studies, often leading to controversies (Schenk et al., 2021).

According to Gutierrez (2015), using SSI in education is essential in enhancing scientific literacy. It makes Science learning more relevant to students' lives and provides a venue for evaluating students' appreciation of the nature of Science and their learning outcomes. It is integral to everyday life and presents valuable opportunities for students to critically analyze the interplay between Science, societal roles, and technology, thereby deepening their understanding of the true essence of SSIs. Educating students about SSIs is essential in fostering their analytical skills, critical thinking abilities, inquiry processes, and communication competencies (Aznam & Irwanto, 2021). With that, SSIs may serve as a good contributor to learning Science and solving practical concerns. Students can effectively evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of learning Science by engaging themselves with relevant, current, and authentic SSIs.

The Department of Education (DepEd) 2016 stated that science education aims to develop scientific literacy among learners, preparing them to be informed and participative citizens who can make judgments and decisions regarding applications of scientific knowledge that may have social, health, or environmental impacts—in addition, based on DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019: Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program: This order provides comprehensive guidelines for implementing the K to 12 curriculum, emphasizing a holistic approach to education that fosters critical thinking, scientific inquiry, and ethical reasoning among students. These elements are essential for developing socio-scientific reasoning skills. This is also supported by the UNESCO Education 2030 Agenda, which advocates for inclusive and equitable quality education that equips learners with the skills to address global challenges, including those involving Science and technology. These provide a basis for integrating socio-scientific reasoning into curricula to prepare students for real-world problem-solving.

Although there is existing research on socio-scientific reasoning, little is known regarding Southeast Asia. In the Philippine context, Talens (2016) highlighted the widespread endorsement among global science educators for SSI-based teaching methodologies. These approaches empower students to acquire practical experiences and apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios. Furthermore, Zeidler et al. (2019) found a gap between the intended goals of science curricula and the actual outcomes in students' reasoning skills. The lack of localized research and evidence-based interventions to address these challenges indicates the need to examine how socio-scientific reasoning can be effectively promoted within the Philippine educational system.

In line with this, in a recently conducted assessment of the science and mathematics reasoning ability of students in one of the biggest senior high schools in Quezon province, results indicate poor performance in terms of science and mathematics literacy, where students obtained 37.50% (Low passed) and 33.33 % (failed) in the mathematics and scientific reasoning skills. The data implies that students performed better in Science and mathematics literacy than in their reasoning skills. Aside from the National Achievement Test (NAT) results, the researcher observed that students exhibited low reasoning skills in Science and Mathematics, as evidenced by the entrance tests administered by the school's guidance counselor. Specifically, out of 100 students, only 28% achieved a passing score in Science and 39% in Mathematics. These findings prompted the researcher to conduct a study to enhance students' reasoning skills in Science, thereby contributing to their overall academic improvement. These findings also highlight an essential connection to socio-scientific reasoning (SSR), as the observed gap in students' scientific and mathematical reasoning abilities underscores a critical challenge in preparing them to tackle real-world issues with social and ethical implications. SSR involves the application of scientific knowledge, ethical reasoning, and interdisciplinary thinking to analyze and address complex societal challenges.

Based on the aforementioned premises, this study addresses a significant gap in the literature by investigating the socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) skills of senior high school (SHS) learners. Specifically, it examined SSR across four dimensions: complexity, perspective-taking, inquiry, and skepticism. Also, the study aimed to identify factors influencing SSR levels among Grade 11 students, focusing on content acquisition, epistemological understanding, and adherence to moral ethics. The findings can inform educational reforms, promote informed citizenship, and contribute to individual development. Prioritizing SSR in education can empower students to become critical thinkers, effective problem solvers, and responsible citizens prepared to address the challenges of the 21st century, thereby contributing to the limited existing research on SSR within the Philippine educational landscape.

Research Questions

This study examined the practices, benefits, and issues of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Thesis Writing. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills of Grade 11 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. Complexity;
 - 1.2. Inquiry;
 - 1.3. Perspective taking; and
 - 1.4. Skepticism?
2. What are the factors affecting the level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1. Content Acquisition;
 - 2.2. Epistemology Scientific Beliefs; and
 - 2.3. Adherence to Moral Ethics?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills and factors affecting the level of socio-scientific reasoning of Grade 11 students?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what interactive video material can be proposed to address the problem of the respondents' socio-scientific reasoning skills?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative data approach wherein conclusions are based on statistical treatment methods. The researcher utilized two research methodologies: an evaluative descriptive survey and a descriptive correlational.

The evaluative descriptive survey was used to measure the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 learners in terms of complexity, inquiry, perspective taking, and skepticism and to identify the factors affecting the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 students.

The descriptive correlational method of research was used to find if there is a significant relationship between the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills and factors affecting the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 students. According to Bhat (2020), a descriptive-correlational research design defines and forecasts how variables are logically linked in the real world without the researcher manipulating or allocating connections between them. It describes the relationship between variables without attempting to establish cause and effect.

An interactive video material titled "The bridge: Connecting Science and Society (SSRS)" to improve the socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 learners was the output of the study. This may help the institution improve Senior High School teachers' teaching strategies and techniques in science-related subjects.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in one of the private schools in Sariaya, Quezon Province. The school offers junior high, senior high, and college courses. It has a total population of 1,253 students in the Senior High School. This locale was chosen because of its existing problem in the socio-scientific reasoning skills of Grade 11 students. Moreover, the research considered this school because of its below-average MPS in Science Subjects and low passing on the Mathematics and Science Reasoning skills entrance examination. The result of the study can help the institution, especially the researcher, who is the institution's assistant principal during the study, to propose seminars and training for teachers to address the issue of socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 learners.

Research Population and Sample

Out of a total population of 597 Grade 11 students from 21 sections, a sample of 236 respondents was selected for the study. The distribution of the sample includes 64 respondents from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, 61 from the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, 37 from the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand, six from the General Academic Strand (GAS), four from the Industrial Arts Electrical (IAE) strand, 16 from the Industrial Arts Automotive (IAA) strand, 15 from the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) strand, and 33 from the Home Economics (HE) strand.

The researcher used stratified random sampling to ensure equal representation across various academic tracks. According to Parsons (2017), it is a sampling method in which several groupings, or strata, are formed from various combinations of attributes in the study population, and a certain number of individuals belonging to each group are sampled. This ensures that subgroups within a population are adequately represented in a sample, leading to more accurate and reliable results, especially when studying diverse populations with distinct characteristics.

Research Instrument

The research utilized a structured questionnaire composed of two parts. The first part was crafted to determine the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills. An adopted questionnaire, derived from William Romine's previous study titled Quantitative Assessment of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills (QuASSR), was utilized for this research. The QuASSR's fundamental framework consists of a concise narrative centered on Socio-Scientific Issues (SSI), followed by a series of multiple-choice questions designed to assess socio-scientific reasoning skills comprehensively. Meanwhile, to measure the level of Socio-Scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 students, the research employed the partial credit model to assess students' selection based on a three (3) level ordinal scale (0=low SSR, 1=Moderate SSR, and 2= high SSR). The multiple questions measured the complexity of two (2) items, perspective taking two (2) items, inquiry -three items (3), and skepticism three (3) items.

The second part was a self-made structure questionnaire to assess the factors affecting socio-scientific reasoning skills among the Grade 11 students regarding content acquisition, epistemology, scientific belief, and adherence to morals and ethics. The variables were interpreted using a four-point Likert scale (1 - Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neutral, 4 - Agree, 5 - Strongly Agree).

To establish the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher sought assistance from 3 validators, a grammarian, a psychologist, and a principal, to validate the content and determine its correctness and appropriateness. Their suggestions were considered for modifying and improving the questionnaire. After working on the revision, the research instrument was distributed for pilot testing in a private school in Quezon Province. The researcher selected 30 Grade 11 students for this and used Cronbach's Alpha to compute the reliability of the questionnaire. The results showed a .910 reliability with an internal consistency of excellent.

After proving that the questionnaire was reliable, the researcher presented the results to the Oral Examination Committee and sought the permission of the members and the Chairperson to administer the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher considered the following stages in collecting and managing data in the study. First, the researcher sought the approval of the principals from one of the biggest senior high schools in Quezon to conduct the study and administer the survey questionnaire to the respondents. Upon request, the researcher distributed the research instrument. The researcher gave the respondents 5 minutes to read the materials and 20 minutes to answer the questions about their socio-scientific reasoning skills. The respondents were given an hour to rest and an additional 20 minutes to answer the second part of the questionnaire to identify the factors affecting the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 learners. The questionnaires were administered in person during the data collection and retrieval from February 22, 2025, to February 28, 2025. Additionally, it is significant that the researcher employed the Tally Tool to organize the collected data systematically. Throughout the data analysis process, the researcher used the IBM SPSS Manual under the institutional license granted to Sacred Heart College of Lucena City.

Statistical Treatment

Data were tabulated for precise analysis and effective presentation of findings. To determine the level of Socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 students in terms of complexity, inquiry, perspective taking, and skepticism and factors affecting the level of Socio-scientific reasoning skills among Grade 11 students in terms of content acquisition, epistemology and adherence to moral ethics, the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was used;

$$WAM = \frac{\sum fw}{n}$$

Wherein,

WAM = Weighted Arithmetic Mean

$\sum fw$ = summation of the product of frequencies and weight

n = total number of responses per Item

In order to arrive at a definite interpretation of results for the statement of problem no. 1, the range was adapted from Sacred Heart College Statistical Guide Revised 2021 on the continuous scale.

Table 1. SSR Socio scientific reasoning skills Scale per Item Basis

Continuum	Qualitative Index
0 .00– 0. 66	Low SSR
0.67 – 1.33	Moderate SSR
1.34 – 2.00	High SSR

Source: QASSRR 2017

In order to arrive at a definite interpretation of results for the statement of problem no. 2, the range was adapted from Sacred Heart College Statistical Guide Revised 2021 on a continuous scale.

Table 2. Weighted average mean per Item Basis

Continuum	Qualitative Index
0 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
2.51 – 3.25	Agree
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Source: Sacred Heart College 2011

A normality test was employed to determine whether a parametric or non-parametric test should be used. The Spearman's Rank Correlation was used to test the relationship between the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills and the factors affecting it:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

The data were tabulated and analyzed using SPSS Data Analysis and Microsoft Tally Tool (2021), and the statistical computation was aided by SPSS, which is licensed to Sacred Heart College.

RESULTS

Part 1 – Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills among Grade 11 Student

Table 1
Level of socio-scientific reasoning skills among grade 11 students in Complexity, perspective-taking, Inquiry and Skepticism.

Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
Complexity	1.65	0.537	High-Level SSR
Perspective Taking	0.88	0.834	Moderate
Inquiry	1.04	0.582	Moderate
Skepticism	0.95	0.592	Moderate
Overall SSR Skills	1.13	0.636	Moderate

Legend:

1.34 – 2.00 = High level SSR

0.66 – 0.0 = low level SSR

1.33 – 0.67 = Moderate SSR

Part 2. Factors Affecting the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills among Grade 11 Students

Table 2
Factors Affecting Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Content Acquisition

Indicators	Frequency				WAM	Qualitative Index
	4	3	2	1		
I have enough knowledge to understand concepts about socio-scientific issues.	24	131	71	10	2.72	Agree
I believe that understanding of scientific content helps me reason about socio-scientific problems.	75	145	12	4	3.23	Agree
I rely on what I learn in class to address socio-scientific issues effectively.	49	154	31	2	3.06	Agree
I use multiple sources, such as books, articles, news, and the internet, to keep up with socio-scientific issues.	64	106	60	6	2.97	Agree
I have a firm grasp of scientific concepts that allow me to analyze, evaluate, and form reasoned arguments about scientific issues.	44	118	69	5	2.85	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean					2.99	Agree

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00 = Strong Agree (SA)

2.51 – 3.25 = Agree (A)

1.76 – 2.50 = Disagree (D)

1.00 – 1.75 = Strong Disagree (SA)

Table 3
Factors Affecting Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in terms of Epistemology
(Scientific Belief)

Indicators	Frequency				WAM	Qualitative Index
	4	3	2	1		
I believe that scientific knowledge is constantly evolving and can be questioned.	80	121	30	5	3.17	Agree
I trust that science can provide solutions to societal problems.	72	138	24	2	3.19	Agree
I consider that it is important to base decisions on scientifically proven information.	82	132	21	1	3.25	Agree
I think it is important to consider different perspectives about socio-scientific issues.	76	138	20	2	3.22	Agree
I am willing to modify personal beliefs when presented with strong scientific evidence.	67	141	24	4	3.15	Agree
Overall WAM					3.19	Agree

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00 = Strong Agree (SA)

2.51 – 3.25 = Agree (A)

1.76 – 2.50 = Disagree (D)

1.00 – 1.75 = Strong Disagree (SA)

Table 4
Factors Affecting Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in terms of Adherence to Moral Ethics

Indicators	Frequency				WAM	Qualitative Index
	4	3	2	1		
I consider the ethical implications of my decisions on socio-scientific issues.	55	152	25	4	3.09	Agree
I prioritize the welfare of people when reasoning about socio-scientific problems.	57	144	31	4	3.08	Agree
I believe it is important to align my decisions on socio-scientific issues with moral values.	70	130	31	5	3.12	Agree

I am aware of the potential and social-ethical consequences of scientific research.	63	130	39	4	3.07	Agree
I can recognize the impact of scientific decisions on human rights and social justice.	55	146	31	4	3.07	Agree
Overall Weighted Average Mean					3.09	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strong Agree (SA) 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D)
 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A) 1.00 – 1.75 – Strong Disagree
(SA)

Part 3 - Significant Relationship Between the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills and Factors Affecting the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning of Grade 11 Students

**Table 5
Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Complexity**

Category	Test of Normality Result	Statistical Tool
A. Content Acquisition	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
B. Epistemology Scientific beliefs	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
C. Adhere to Moral Ethics	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
D. Overall WAM	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)

Table 6
Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Complexity and Factors Affecting the level of SSR

Variables being correlated	df	Mean	ρ value	t-value	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significant
Complexity(x ₁) vs Content(x ₂) Acquisition	234	x ₁ =1.65 Vs x ₂ =2.96	-.008	-.12	.904	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Complexity(x ₁) vs Epistemology Scientific Beliefs(x ₃)	234	x ₁ =1.65 Vs x ₃ =3.19	.103	1.59	.113	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Complexity(x ₁) vs Adhere to Moral Ethics(x ₄)	234	x ₁ =1.65 Vs x ₄ =3.09	.143	2.22	.028	Reject Ho	Significant
Complexity(x ₁) vs Overall Factors(x ₅)	234	x ₁ =1.65 Vs x ₅ = 3.12	.116	1.78	.075	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 7
Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Inquiry

Category	Test of Normality Result	Statistical Tool
A. Content Acquisition	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
B. Epistemology Scientific beliefs	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
C. Adhere to Moral Ethics	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
D. Overall WAM	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)

Table 8
Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Inquiry and Factors Affecting the Level of SSR

Variables being correlated	Df	Mean	ρ value	t-value	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significant
Inquiry (x ₁) Vs Content Acquisition(x ₂)	234	x ₁ = 1.04 Vs X ₂ = 2.96	.030	.459	.646	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Inquiry(x ₁) Vs Epistemology Scientific Beliefs (x ₃)	234	x ₁ =1.04 Vs x ₃ = 3.19	-.081	-1.243	.214	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Inquiry (x ₁) Vs Adhere to Moral Ethics (x ₄)	234	x ₁ =1.04 Vs x ₄ = 3.09	-.026	-.398	.689	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Inquiry (x ₁) Vs Overall Factors (x ₅)	234	x ₁ = 1.04 Vs x ₅ = 3.12	-.006	-.092	.931	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 9
Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Perspective Taking

Category	Test of Normality Result	Statistical Tool
A. Content Acquisition	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
B. Epistemology Scientific beliefs	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
C. Adhere to Moral Ethics	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
D. Overall WAM	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)

Table 10
Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Perspective Taking and Factors Affecting the Level of SSR

Variables being correlated	df	Mean	ρ value	t-value	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significant
Perspective Taking (x ₁) Vs Content Acquisition (x ₂)	234	x ₁ =.88 Vs x ₂ = 2.96	.034	.521	.603	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Perspective Taking(x ₁) Vs Epistemology Scientific Beliefs (x ₃)	234	x ₁ =.88 Vs x ₃ = 3.19	.056	.862	.390	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Perspective Taking(x ₁) Vs Adhere to Moral Ethics(x ₄)	234	x ₁ =.88 Vs x ₄ = 3.09	.019	.299	.766	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Perspective Taking(x ₁) Vs Overall Factors (x ₅)	234	x ₁ =.88 Vs x ₅ =3.12	.062	.948	.344	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Table 11
Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Skepticism

Category	Test of Normality Result	Statistical Tool
A. Content Acquisition	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
B. Epistemology Scientific beliefs	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
C. Adhere to Moral Ethics	Not Normal	Non-parametric Test

D. Overall WAM	Not Normal	(Spearman's rank correlation) Non-parametric Test (Spearman's rank correlation)
----------------	------------	---

Table 12
Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Skepticism and Factors Affecting the level of SSR

Variables being correlated	df	Mean	ρ value	t-value	p-value	Decision	Impression at 0.05 level of significant
Skepticism (x ₁) Vs Content Acquisition (x ₂)	234	x ₁ =.95 Vs x ₂ =2.96	.049	0.746	.456	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Skepticism (x ₁) Vs Epistemology Scientific Beliefs (x ₃)	234	x ₁ =.95 Vs x ₃ =3.19	.144	2.213	.027	Failed to accept Ho	Significant
Skepticism (x ₁) Vs Adhere to Moral Ethics (x ₄)	234	x ₁ =.95 Vs x ₄ =3.09	.047	0.723	.470	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Skepticism (x ₁) Vs Overall Factors (x ₅)	234	x ₁ =.95 Vs x ₅ =3.12	.051	0.779	.437	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 highlights the socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) abilities of grade 11 students, specifically evaluating their proficiency in four key areas: Complexity, Perspective-taking, Inquiry, and Skepticism. Among these measured skills, Complexity emerges where students exhibit the strongest performance. With a mean score of 1.65 and a standard deviation of 0.537, the results suggest a high level of competence in understanding and analyzing the Complexity of socio-scientific issues. This means that students are adept at identifying and comprehending the multifaceted nature of these issues, considering various factors and interconnected elements involved. Their ability to navigate this Complexity may reflect strengths in recognizing nuances and intricacies within socio-scientific contexts, which is vital for informed decision-making and critical thinking.

This result aligns with the study by Ibardeola et al. (2022), which investigates the connection between social media exposure and students' awareness of societal issues. It concludes that while social media exposure does not directly enhance students' level of awareness, it significantly contributes to their active and radical involvement in addressing these challenges. This suggests that social media is a platform for fostering student engagement rather than merely raising awareness.

On the other hand, perspective-taking has the lowest means score of 0.88 and a high standard deviation of 0.834 with the interpretation of Moderate SSR, which shows a potential area of weakness. The high standard deviations suggest a wide range of group perspective-taking abilities. Some individuals may be pretty good at it, while others struggle significantly; this indicates that students' analysis of SSI Socio-scientific issues from multiple perspectives and appreciation of the unique concerns of various stakeholders need enhancement for the students to understand the socio-scientific issues better and respect different viewpoints and consider the interest of different stakeholders. Macalalag et al. (2024) explored the role of SSI in promoting social justice and equity in education. They found that SSI-based teaching encourages students to engage in reflective scientific Skepticism and consider societal issues' moral and ethical dimensions.

Similarly, the Inquiry obtained a mean of 1.04 and a standard deviation of 0.582, which is interpreted as moderate SSR. The results show that students understand that Socio-scientific issues are subject to ongoing Inquiry and are relatively able to identify the missing information to solve societal issues using their socio-scientific reasoning skills; this implies that students can identify some missing information but struggle to identify all data consistently to solve the societal issue. Osborne et al. (2020) examined students' proficiency in evaluating evidence within scientific contexts and revealed that this challenge becomes more pronounced when confronted with complex, multifaceted societal problems.

The results of Skepticism ($M=0.95$, $SD=0.5582$) are similar to those of Inquiry and Perspective taking; the mean interpretation for Skepticism is moderate SSR. The data shows that students exhibit reflective Skepticism in processing and analyzing information about SSI from a potential bias. However, this Skepticism is at an average level. Students have a fair ability to assess and evaluate the information they receive about socio-scientific issues. The ability of students to assess and evaluate information regarding socio-scientific issues (SSI) has been extensively studied in recent years. Research highlights SSI-based education's role in fostering students' critical thinking and decision-making skills. Macalalag et al. (2024) explored the impact of SSI on promoting social justice and equity in education. They found that students engaged in SSI-based learning exhibited improved reflexivity and metacognition, essential for assessing and evaluating information effectively.

Combining all domains, the overall mean score is 1.13 with a standard deviation of 0.636, interpreted as a "Moderate" level. This indicates that while students show promising development in understanding Complexity, their general socio-scientific

reasoning skills across all domains are moderately developed. They could benefit from targeted interventions in perspective-taking, Inquiry, and Skepticism. This finding was supported by Badeo and Duque (2022), who conducted a meta-analysis on the integration of socio-scientific issues (SSI) in science education. Their findings revealed that while students demonstrate moderate SSR skills, there is a need for targeted interventions to enhance their ability to analyze and address complex societal problems critically.

Part 2. Factors Affecting the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills among Grade 11 Students

Table 2 provides insight into the factors influencing socio-scientific reasoning skills, focusing specifically on the role of content acquisition. The data indicate that all measured indicators have a qualitative index of Agree, suggesting that students generally acknowledge the significance of acquiring scientific content knowledge in enhancing their reasoning skills in socio-scientific contexts. The Overall Weighted Average Mean (WAM) of 2.99 further supports the conclusion that content acquisition is widely recognized as an important factor, with the qualitative index again interpreted as Agree.

Among the indicators, the statement *"I believe that understanding of scientific content helps me reason about socio-scientific problems."* received the highest WAM of 3.23 and a qualitative index of Agree. This result highlights the strong belief among students that a solid grasp of scientific content directly aids in their ability to analyze and reason through socio-scientific challenges. It emphasizes the importance of equipping learners with robust scientific knowledge to empower them in addressing complex socio-scientific issues.

This finding relates to the study of Putri et al. (2019), who suggest that implementing a Levels of Inquiry model centered on SSIs significantly improved students' scientific reasoning and argumentative skills. By engaging in structured Inquiry, students develop a deeper understanding of scientific concepts while learning to construct well-supported arguments. Moreover, these highlight the importance of considering students' diverse resources and creating supportive learning environments that encourage critical thinking and informed decision-making. Providing such opportunities ensures that students can effectively analyze and engage with real-world scientific challenges.

On the other hand, the indicator *"I feel I have enough knowledge understanding concepts about socio-scientific issues."* scored the lowest WAM of 2.72. However, it still retains the qualitative index of Agree. This suggests that while students recognize the importance of understanding scientific concepts, some may feel less confident about the adequacy of their knowledge in this area. It implies potential gaps or limitations in their perceived content mastery, which may affect their ability to engage with socio-scientific reasoning tasks fully. These results imply that students understand that scientific knowledge is vital in making decisions to solve societal problems. Scientific content can be utilized to draw conclusions and discuss socio-scientific issues that affect society.

Studies indicate that students' socio-scientific reasoning and ability to acquire scientific content are strongly affected by their prior knowledge and cognitive abilities. A solid foundation in scientific concepts allows students to engage more effectively in discussions and problem-solving related to socio-scientific issues. Moreover, research highlights that scientific reasoning skills are crucial in shaping content knowledge acquisition. For instance, Stender et al. (2018) found that these reasoning skills directly contribute to learning gains, especially in inquiry-based activities where students explore scientific concepts through investigation and analysis. This suggests that fostering cognitive development and strengthening reasoning abilities can significantly enhance students' capacity to understand and apply scientific knowledge in real-world contexts.

Table 3

Factors Affecting Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in terms of Epistemology (Scientific Belief)

Table 3 on the next page shows the factors affecting socio-scientific reasoning skills regarding Epistemology (Scientific Belief). All indicators have a qualitative index of agree and got an overall WAM of 3.19, which has a qualitative index of Agree which indicates that the students generally recognize the importance of scientific principles and evidence in shaping their reasoning abilities.

The statement *"I consider that it is important to base decisions on scientifically proven information"* received the highest WAM of 3.25, interpreted as Agree. This result underscores students' emphasis on scientifically validated data as the foundation for decision-making in socio-scientific contexts. It reflects their strong appreciation for the reliability and objectivity of scientific evidence in addressing complex problems. Therefore, epistemological scientific beliefs significantly shape how students engage with socio-scientific reasoning (SSR). Yang et al. (2019) emphasized that students who view scientific knowledge as evolving and evidence-based tend to exhibit higher reasoning skills and academic performance. Their study, conducted among students in Taiwan and India, highlighted how educational systems and cultural backgrounds shape the development of epistemic beliefs. These beliefs subsequently influence students' understanding and responses to real-world scientific challenges. The findings suggest that a stronger emphasis on epistemology in science education could enhance socio-scientific reasoning (SSR).

Consequently, *"I am willing to modify personal belief when presented with strong scientific evidence"* scored the lowest WAM of 3.15, yet it still carries the qualitative index of Agree. This implies that while students acknowledge the importance of adapting their beliefs based on compelling scientific evidence, some may face challenges or hesitation in fully embracing changes to their established perspectives. This could reflect a degree of cognitive resistance or the need for further development in critical acceptance of evidence. Similarly, Lindfors et al. (2019) claim that students who understand that knowledge is not absolute and is subject to change approach such challenges more analytically and thoughtfully. This capacity to manage uncertainty is fundamental to developing strong SSR. Therefore, educational environments should incorporate ill-structured problems to foster students' reasoning skills and epistemological awareness.

Table 4

Factors Affecting Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in terms of Adherence to Moral Ethics

Table 4 on the succeeding page shows the factors affecting socio-scientific reasoning skills in terms of adherence to moral ethics. The data indicate that all the measured indicators have a qualitative index of Agree, reflecting a generally positive acknowledgment of the importance of adhering to moral and ethical principles when reasoning about socio-scientific issues. The overall WAM is 3.09, with a qualitative index of Agree.

The statement *"I believe it is important to align my decisions on socio-scientific issues with moral values"* received the highest WAM of 3.12. This result underscores students' strong emphasis on moral principles as a foundational guide for making decisions on complex socio-scientific matters. It reflects their commitment to ensuring their reasoning aligns with ethical standards and values, demonstrating a sense of moral responsibility. The results imply that moral values must be considered when deciding to solve socio-scientific issues. Recent studies emphasize the critical role of moral values in decision-making processes, particularly in addressing socio-scientific issues. Paraskeva-Hadjichambi et al. (2015) explored how students' decisions on environmental socio-scientific issues are intertwined with their values. Their findings revealed that students often prioritize criteria aligned with their moral and ethical beliefs, significantly influencing their decision-making strategies. The study highlighted the importance of fostering value-based reasoning to enable students to balance conflicting criteria effectively.

Two indicators tied for the lowest WAM of 3.07, carrying the qualitative Agree index. These are: *"I am aware of the potential and social ethical consequences of scientific research."* and *"I can recognize the impact of scientific decisions on human rights and social justice."* While these scores are still interpreted positively, they suggest slightly less confidence or emphasis in these areas. This may point to a need for enhancing students' understanding and awareness of the broader societal and ethical implications of scientific research and decisions. Gutierrez (2015) investigated the integration of socio-scientific issues in biology education to enhance bioethical decision-making skills. The research demonstrated that incorporating these issues into the curriculum improved students' scientific literacy and encouraged them to consider moral and ethical dimensions in their reasoning. This approach was found to promote more informed and balanced decision-making. These studies underscore the necessity of integrating moral and ethical considerations into educational frameworks to address the complexities of socio-scientific issues. By doing so, students can develop a more holistic understanding of the interplay between scientific evidence and moral values, leading to more thoughtful and responsible decision-making.

Part 3 - Significant Relationship Between the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills and Factors Affecting the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning of Grade 11 Students

Table 5

Table 5 summarizes the results of the normality tests, which were crucial for determining whether a parametric or non-parametric test should be used. The analysis indicated that the data for content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, and adherence to moral ethics were not normally distributed but had homogeneous variances in Complexity. Given these findings, parametric tests assuming normality were deemed unsuitable for these categories. Therefore, Spearman's rank correlation, a non-parametric test, was implemented to analyze the relationships within these data sets. Spearman's rank correlation does not require the normality assumption, making it an appropriate choice for these non-normally distributed but homogeneous data sets.

In contrast, the data for overall WAM were neither normally distributed nor homogeneous in terms of Complexity. This indicated that neither parametric tests nor tests assuming homogeneity of variances would be appropriate. Consequently, Spearman's rank correlation was also employed for this category. As a non-parametric test, Spearman's rank correlation was suitable for analyzing the relationships within the overall WAM data set despite its lack of normality and homogeneity. Using this non-parametric test, the analysis could proceed confidently, ensuring valid and reliable results for the given data sets.

Table 6 on the next page displays the results of Spearman's rank correlation test, revealing the significant factors that influence socio-scientific reasoning skills about Complexity.

Table 6

Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Complexity and Factors Affecting the level of SSR

The rho test results showed that Complexity was not significantly correlated with Content Acquisition ($M_{\text{Complexity}} = 1.65$, $M_{\text{Content}} = 2.96$, $\rho = -0.008$, $t = -0.12$, $p = 0.907$). The correlation coefficient -0.008 indicated a weak negative relationship between Complexity and content acquisition. The t-value of -0.12 was close to zero, suggesting no significant difference. The result was not statistically significant since the p-value was 0.904 (much greater than 0.05). Thus, the data failed to reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there was no significant relationship between Complexity and content acquisition. This finding aligns with the study of Quintana, R. (2022), "Embracing Complexity in Social Science Research," which investigated the interdependencies between causal factors, often called causal Complexity. The research emphasized the importance of understanding how the interaction or combination of different factors generates specific outcomes. The study highlighted that Complexity in socio-scientific reasoning did not significantly affect content acquisition.

The rho test results showed that Complexity was not significantly correlated with Epistemology Scientific Beliefs ($M_{\text{Epistemology}} = 3.19$, $\rho = 0.103$, $t = 1.59$, $p = 0.113$). The correlation coefficient 0.103 indicated a very weak positive relationship between

complexity and epistemological scientific beliefs. The t-value of 1.59 was not enough to show a significant difference. The result was not statistically significant since the p-value was 0.113 (greater than 0.05). Thus, the data failed to reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there was no significant relationship between complexity and epistemological scientific beliefs.

The rho test results showed that Complexity was significantly correlated with Adherence to Moral Ethics ($M_{\text{Adhere}} = 3.09$, $\rho = 0.143$, $t = 2.22$, $p = 0.028$). The correlation coefficient of 0.143 indicated a weak positive relationship between Complexity and adherence to moral ethics. The t-value of 2.22 suggested there was enough evidence to show a significant difference. The result was statistically significant since the p-value was 0.028, less than the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the data failed to accept the null hypothesis and concluded that there was a significant relationship between Complexity and adherence to moral ethics.

The rho test results showed that Complexity was not significantly correlated with Overall Factors ($M = 3.12$, $\rho = .116$, $t = 1.78$, $p = 0.75$). The correlation coefficient of .116 indicated a weak relationship between Complexity and overall factors. The t value of 1.78 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.75 (much greater than 0.05), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Inquiry and overall factors.

The results revealed that only adherence to moral ethics showed a statistically significant relationship with Complexity. This meant that individuals with higher Complexity in their reasoning tended to adhere more to moral and ethical principles. There was no significant relationship between Complexity for content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, and overall factors. Therefore, these factors did not show a meaningful correlation with Complexity in the context of the study. Comparably, Zeidler et al. (2019) investigated how socio-scientific issues enhance scientific literacy. They highlighted the significance of perspective-taking and critical reasoning within the context of interdisciplinary science education.

Table 7

Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Inquiry

Table 7 provides a detailed summary of the normality tests, which were essential in determining whether a parametric or non-parametric test should be employed. The analysis revealed that the data for content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, and adherence to moral ethics did not follow a normal distribution but had homogeneous variances in terms of Inquiry. Given these findings, parametric tests assuming normality were deemed unsuitable for these categories. Therefore, Spearman's rank correlation, a non-parametric test, was implemented to analyze the relationships within these data sets. Spearman's rank correlation does not require the normality assumption, making it an appropriate choice for these non-normally distributed but homogeneous data sets.

Similarly, the data for overall WAM were not normally distributed but had homogeneous variances in Inquiry. Although parametric tests were unsuitable due to the lack of normality, the homogeneity of variances allowed for non-parametric tests. Consequently, Spearman's rank correlation was also employed for this category. As a non-parametric test, Spearman's rank correlation was well-suited for analyzing the relationships within the overall WAM data set despite its non-normal distribution. Using this non-parametric test, the analysis proceeded confidently, ensuring valid and reliable results for the given data sets.

Table 8

Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Inquiry and Factors Affecting the Level of SSR

Table 8 presents the results of Spearman's rank correlation test, highlighting the significant factors associated with the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills about Inquiry.

The rho test results showed that Inquiry was not significantly correlated with Content Acquisition ($M_{\text{Inquiry}} = 1.04$, $M_{\text{Content}} = 2.96$, $\rho = 0.030$, $t = 0.459$, $p = 0.646$). The correlation coefficient of 0.030 indicated a weak positive relationship between inquiry and content acquisition. The t-value of 0.459 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.646 (much greater than 0.05), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between inquiry and content acquisition.

The rho test results showed that Inquiry was not significantly correlated with Epistemology Scientific Beliefs ($M_{\text{Epistemology}} = 3.19$, $\rho = -0.081$, $t = -1.243$, $p = 0.214$). The correlation coefficient of -0.081 indicated a very weak negative relationship between inquiry and epistemology scientific beliefs. The t-value of -1.243 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.214 (greater than 0.05), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between inquiry and epistemology scientific beliefs. Research has shown that inquiry-based learning can have varying effects on content acquisition. For instance, Martin et al. (2022) examined the Community of Inquiry (CoI) presence and learning outcomes in online and blended learning environments. They found that cognitive presence, closely related to Inquiry, had a weak correlation with actual learning outcomes ($r = .250$) (Martin et al., 2022).

The rho test results showed that Inquiry was not significantly correlated with Adherence to Moral Ethics ($M_{\text{Adhere}} = 3.09$, $\rho = -0.026$, $t = -0.398$, $p = 0.689$). The correlation coefficient of -0.026 indicated a weak negative relationship between Inquiry and adherence to moral ethics. The t-value of -0.398 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.689 (much greater than 0.05), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Inquiry and adherence to moral ethics. Furthermore, the role of philosophy in understanding ethics and morality has been explored extensively. The Online Business

School (2025) study emphasized the importance of philosophical frameworks in ethical reasoning and moral values, suggesting that ethical theories and moral beliefs are influenced by various factors beyond inquiry-based learning (Online Business School, 2025).

The rho test results showed that Inquiry was not significantly correlated with Overall Factors ($M = 3.12$, $\rho = -0.006$, $t = -0.092$, $p = 0.931$). The correlation coefficient -0.006 indicated a weak negative relationship between Inquiry and overall factors. The t -value of -0.092 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p -value was 0.931 (much greater than 0.05), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Inquiry and overall factors.

The analysis showed that Inquiry did not correlate statistically with content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, adherence to moral ethics, or overall factors. The p -values for all these relationships exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold, concluding that there was no significant relationship between Inquiry and any of these factors. This meant that variations in Inquiry did not meaningfully relate to variations in these factors. Studies indicate that inquiry-based learning influences content acquisition, scientific epistemological beliefs, and adherence to moral ethics in various ways. For example, Wang et al. (2022) investigated the impact of structured and open Inquiry on secondary students' scientific and mathematical literacies. Their findings revealed that open-inquiry activities were negatively associated with students' literacy in these areas. In contrast, structured inquiry learning and epistemological beliefs about science were significant and positive predictors of student literacy performance (Wang et al., 2022).

Table 9

Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Perspective Taking

Table 9 provides a detailed summary of the normality tests, which were essential in determining whether to employ a parametric or non-parametric test. The analysis revealed that the data for content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, and adherence to moral ethics did not follow a normal distribution regarding perspective-taking. However, the variances for content acquisition and epistemology scientific beliefs were homogeneous, while the variance for adherence to moral ethics was not homogeneous.

Given these findings, parametric tests assuming normality were deemed unsuitable for these categories. As a result, Spearman's rank correlation, a non-parametric test, was implemented to analyze the relationships within these data sets. Spearman's rank correlation does not require the assumption of normality, making it an appropriate choice for these non-normally distributed data sets, regardless of their variance homogeneity.

Similarly, the data for overall WAM were not normally distributed but had homogeneous variances in perspective-taking. Although parametric tests were unsuitable

due to the lack of normality, the homogeneity of variances allowed for non-parametric tests. Consequently, Spearman's rank correlation was employed for this category as well. Using this non-parametric test, the analysis proceeded confidently, ensuring valid and reliable results for the given data sets. This approach allowed for a more accurate interpretation of the relationships within the data, considering the non-normal distribution and varying homogeneity of the variances.

Table 10

Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Perspective Taking and Factors Affecting the Level of SSR

Table 10 on the next page presents the results of Spearman's rank correlation test, showing the significant factors influencing the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills about Perspective.

The rho test results show that Perspective was not significantly correlated with Content Acquisition ($M_{\text{Perspective}} = 0.88$, $M_{\text{Content}} = 2.96$, $\rho = 0.034$, $t = 0.521$, $p = 0.603$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) 0.034 indicated a weak positive relationship between Perspective and content acquisition.

The t-value of 0.521 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.603 (much greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Perspective and content acquisition. Tomasello's (2020) research delved into the cognitive underpinnings of perspective-taking and its importance in social cognition. The study underscored that, although perspective-taking is crucial for understanding others, its connection with unrelated cognitive variables like content acquisition and epistemological beliefs is minimal.

The rho test results showed that Perspective was not significantly correlated with Epistemology Scientific Beliefs ($M_{\text{Epistemology}} = 3.19$, $\rho = 0.056$, $t = 0.862$, $p = 0.390$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.056 indicated a very weak positive relationship between perspective and epistemology scientific beliefs. The t-value of 0.862 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.390 (greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between perspective and epistemology scientific beliefs.

The rho test results showed that Perspective was not significantly correlated with Adherence to Moral Ethics ($M_{\text{Adhere}} = 3.09$, $\rho = 0.019$, $t = 0.299$, $p = 0.766$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.019 indicated a weak positive relationship between Perspective and adherence to moral ethics. The t-value of 0.299 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.766 (much greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Perspective and adherence to moral ethics.

The rho test results show that Perspective was not significantly correlated with Overall Factors ($M = 3.12$, $\rho = 0.062$, $t = 0.948$, $p = 0.344$). The correlation coefficient (ρ)

0.062 indicated a weak positive relationship between Perspective and overall factors. The t-value of 0.948 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.344 (greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Perspective and overall factors.

The analysis shows that Perspective did not correlate statistically with content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, adherence to moral ethics, or overall factors. The p-values for all these relationships exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold, concluding that there was no significant relationship between Perspective and any of these factors. This meant that variations in Perspective did not meaningfully relate to variations in these factors.

This study is related to the work of Guo et al. (2022) on the relationship between epistemological beliefs, reflective thinking, and science identity. Their study, published in the *International Journal of STEM Education*, constructs a model to explore this relationship and highlights these variables' direct and indirect effects on students' science identity. (Article 40, Volume 9).

Table 11 on the next page provides a detailed summary of the normality tests, which were essential in determining whether to employ a parametric or non-parametric test. The analysis revealed that the data for content acquisition, epistemology, scientific beliefs, adherence to moral ethics, and overall WAM did not follow a normal distribution but had homogeneous variances in terms of Skepticism.

Table 11

Tests of Normality of the Level of Socio-Scientific Reasoning Skills in Terms of Skepticism

Given these findings, parametric tests assuming normality were deemed unsuitable for these categories. As a result, Spearman's rank correlation, a non-parametric test, was implemented to analyze the relationships within these data sets. Spearman's rank correlation does not require the assumption of normality or homogeneity of variances, making it an appropriate choice for these non-normally distributed data sets.

Using Spearman's rank correlation allowed for a robust analysis of the relationships within the data, ensuring valid and reliable results despite the lack of normality. By adopting this non-parametric test, the analysis could proceed confidently, providing meaningful insights into the data while accounting for its non-normal distribution and homogeneous variances. This approach facilitated a more accurate interpretation of the relationships within the data, accommodating the specific characteristics of the data sets.

Table 12

Specific Test Result on Finding the Significant Relationship between Skepticism and Factors Affecting the level of SSR

The rho test results showed that Skepticism was not significantly correlated with Content Acquisition ($M_{\text{Skepticism}} = 0.95$, $M_{\text{Content}} = 2.96$, $\rho = 0.049$, $t = 0.746$, $p = 0.456$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) 0.049 indicated a weak positive relationship between Skepticism and content acquisition. The t-value of 0.746 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.456 (greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Skepticism and content acquisition. This study is aligned with the findings of Irmak (2020) on socio-scientific reasoning competencies and the nature of science conceptions among undergraduate students from different faculties. Irmak's study, published in *Science Education International*, investigated the SSR competencies and nature of science conceptions of these students and found that Skepticism did not significantly impact content acquisition (Vol. 31, No. 1, pp. 65-73).

The rho test results showed that Skepticism was significantly correlated with Epistemology Scientific Beliefs ($M_{\text{Epistemology}} = 3.19$, $\rho = 0.144$, $t = 2.213$, $p = 0.027$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.144 indicated a weak positive relationship between skepticism and epistemology scientific beliefs. The t-value of 2.213 suggested that this relationship was statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.027 (less than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data rejected the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between skepticism and epistemology scientific beliefs. This suggested that higher levels of Skepticism were associated with stronger epistemology and scientific beliefs. This study aligned with the findings of Ramírez-i-Ollé (2019) on the interplay between trust, Skepticism, and social order within the context of scientific knowledge. Ramírez-i-Ollé's paper, published in *Sociology Compass*, explored the interplay between trust, Skepticism, and social order, demonstrating that Skepticism was intricately linked to epistemological beliefs and cognitive order.

The rho test results showed that Skepticism was not significantly correlated with Adherence to Moral Ethics ($M_{\text{Adhere}} = 3.09$, $\rho = 0.047$, $t = 0.723$, $p = 0.470$). The correlation coefficient (ρ) of 0.047 indicated a weak positive relationship between Skepticism and adherence to moral ethics. The t-value of 0.723 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.470 (greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Skepticism and adherence to moral ethics. Clearfield's (2018) study, *Skepticism, Relativism, and Truth*, aligned with the findings that Skepticism does not significantly impact adherence to moral ethics. This syllabus from Whitman College discussed various forms of Skepticism and relativism, along with the responses from proponents of objective truth, indicating that Skepticism did not substantially affect adherence to moral ethics (pp. 20-35).

The rho test results showed that Skepticism was not significantly correlated with Overall Factors ($M_{\text{Overall}} = 3.12$, $\rho = 0.051$, $t = 0.779$, $p = 0.437$). The correlation coefficient

(p) 0.051 indicated a weak positive relationship between Skepticism and overall factors. The t-value of 0.779 suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. Since the p-value was 0.437 (greater than the 0.05 significance threshold), the data failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship between Skepticism and overall factors. This study aligned with the findings of Irmak (2020) on socio-scientific reasoning competencies and the nature of science conceptions among undergraduate students from different faculties. Irmak (2020) study, published in *Science Education International*, investigated the SSR competencies and nature of science conceptions of these students and found that Skepticism did not significantly impact overall factors in the level of socio-scientific reasoning

The analysis showed that Skepticism did not correlate statistically with content acquisition, adherence to moral ethics, or overall factors. The p-values for all these relationships exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold, concluding that there was no significant relationship between Skepticism and these factors. This meant that variations in Skepticism did not meaningfully relate to variations in content acquisition, adherence to moral ethics, or overall factors. For epistemology scientific beliefs, there was a statistically significant relationship with Skepticism. The p-value of 0.027 (less than 0.05) suggested that higher levels of Skepticism were associated with stronger epistemology and scientific beliefs. This finding indicated that Skepticism positively influenced individuals' scientific beliefs and understanding. This study aligned with Herman. et al (2019) findings on recent trends in socio-scientific issues research. Their paper, published in *Disciplinary and Interdisciplinary Science Education Research*, emphasized the central role of socio-scientific reasoning and highlighted that Skepticism was intricately linked to various factors in SSR (Article 11, Volume).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

1. Students demonstrate strength in grasping complex socio-scientific issues but also show areas where improvement is needed to achieve a more balanced and advanced development in SSR skills. Moderate scores in perspective-taking, Inquiry, and Skepticism highlight opportunities for targeted interventions or educational strategies to enhance these dimensions.
2. Students value content acquisition as a foundational aspect of SSR, highlighting its importance in providing the necessary knowledge base for informed decision-making. It also demonstrates their understanding of how epistemological beliefs, such as reliance on scientifically proven information and openness to modifying beliefs based on evidence, are critical components in fostering rational and evidence-based reasoning. Furthermore, their acknowledgment of adherence to moral ethics emphasizes the importance of aligning decisions with ethical principles, human rights, and social justice in socio-scientific contexts.

3. Variations in Complexity, Inquiry, and Skepticism do not meaningfully influence or correlate with the combined factors of SSR skills within this context. This highlights the independence of these domains from the measured SSR factors, suggesting the need for targeted strategies to strengthen these specific areas and their integration into broader socio-scientific reasoning frameworks.

4. The study's development of interactive video material provides a practical and user-friendly solution for addressing the gaps in socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) skills among respondents. By focusing on essential areas such as Complexity, perspective-taking, Inquiry, and Skepticism, these materials provide an engaging and accessible way to enhance learners' critical thinking and analytical abilities. This approach emphasizes the importance of visually appealing resources in fostering more profound understanding and skill development. Thus, this output is a valuable educational tool, empowering students to navigate complex real-world challenges more effectively.

Recommendations

In the light of the results of this study, the following recommendations were formulated:

1. To enhance socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) among students, they can use the provided interactive video material and other educational resources to enhance their SSR skills in Complexity, perspective-taking, Inquiry, and Skepticism.
2. To support students in strengthening their socio-scientific reasoning (SSR), it is recommended to integrate educational strategies that emphasize content acquisition as a foundation for informed decision-making. This can be achieved by providing students with access to scientifically proven information, encouraging openness to modifying beliefs based on evidence, and fostering critical discussions around epistemological principles. Additionally, ethical frameworks should be embedded into the curriculum, ensuring that decision-making processes align with moral ethics, human rights, and social justice.
3. To address the independence of Complexity, Inquiry, and Skepticism from the combined factors of SSR skills, it is recommended that targeted strategies be implemented to enhance these domains while fostering their integration into broader socio-scientific reasoning frameworks.
4. The teachers can disseminate the output of this study to the students to measure and determine the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills. They can integrate interactive video material into their lessons to make socio-scientific concepts more accessible and engaging for students.
5. The academic coordinator may organize professional development workshops for teachers focused on teaching strategies to enhance SSR skills.

6. Administrators should utilize the results of the study, particularly Inquiry, perspective-taking, and Skepticism, to obtain the lowest mean in terms of the level of socio-scientific reasoning skills by designing projects and programs that can enhance the socio-scientific reasoning skills of the students.
7. The study may guide future researchers who aim to conduct comparable or related studies about this topic. The research's findings may serve as the foundation for related theoretical frameworks. Similarly, future researchers may enhance or add to the output that was the final goal of the current study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethics in research deals primarily with the interaction between the researcher and the participants under study. This means that the well-being of research participants must be the top priority whenever one conducts research. In this study, ethical consideration was done by ensuring that the individuals, organizations, and institutions involved in the reports were made anonymous. As a result, the researcher made it clear to all participants that their involvement was optional and that they might opt out at any moment. The researcher made it clear that any information that came from the respondents and sample would remain confidential. All respondents were requested to sign a permission form indicating their willingness to engage in the study while maintaining confidentiality and anonymity. To ensure the security and confidentiality of the data gathered, all information is stored in a password-protected Google Drive folder, accessible only to the researcher. Once the study is completed and the data is no longer needed, it will be disposed of responsibly by permanently deleting the files from the Google Drive folder. This ensures that sensitive information is securely eliminated, adhering to ethical standards for research data management. Lastly, all the citations from different authors were appropriately cited.

REFERENCES

- Açıkgöz, H., & Akman, B. (2023). The relationship between epistemological beliefs and technological pedagogical content knowledge in teachers. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), Article 12.
- Aznan, N., & Irwanto, I. (2021). Socio-Scientific Issues as a Vehicle to Promote Soft Skills and Environmental Awareness. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 10(1), 161-174. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.10.1.161>
- Badeo, J. M., & Duque, D. A. (2022). The Effect of Socio-Scientific Issues (SSI) in Teaching Science: A Meta-Analysis Study. *Journal of Technology and Science Education*, 12(2), 291-302. <https://www.jotse.org/index.php/jotse/article/view/1340/610>
- Clearfield, M. (2018). *Philosophy 137: Skepticism, Relativism, and Truth*. In Whitman College.

- Department of Education. (2016). K to 12 science curriculum guide. DO 55, s. 2016 – Policy Guidelines on the National Assessment of Student Learning for the K to 12 Basic Education Program | Department of Education. (n.d.). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2016/06/30/do-55-s-2016-policy-guidelines-on-the-national-assessment-of-student-learning-for-the-k-to-12-basic-education-program/>
- De Lillo, C., & Ferguson, H. (2023). Perspective-taking and social inferences: The role of executive functions in enhancing social interactions. *Journal of Cognitive Development*, 45(2), 123-137.
- Evagorou, M., Jiménez-Aleixandre, M. P., & Osborne, J. (2020). Developing critical and epistemic thinking in socio-scientific issues. *Science Education*, 104(5), 846-855.
- Gutierrez, S. B. (2015). Integrating socio-scientific issues to enhance the bioethical decision-making skills of high school students. *International Education Studies*, 8(1), 142-151. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1060853>
- Guo, J., Wang, X., & Liu, H. (2022). The role of epistemological beliefs in reflective thinking and science identity. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 114(4), 756-772.
- Ho, L. W., Chen, X., & Yang, J. (2021). Perspective-taking and its effects on professional skepticism: The moderating role of incentives.
- Ibardoza, K. B., Badillo, L. T., Macatangay, J. M. H., Dela Cruz, K. R., & Malabanan, M. P. (2022). Students' exposure to social media and their radical involvement on the
- Irmak, M. (2020). Socioscientific Reasoning Competencies and Nature of Science Conceptions of Undergraduate Students from Different Faculties. *Science Education International*, 31(1), 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.33828/sei.v31.i1.7>
- Martin, F., Wu, T., Wan, L., & Xie, K. (2022). A meta-analysis of the Community of Inquiry presences and learning outcomes in online and blended learning environments. *Online Learning*, 26(1), 325-359. DOI: 10.24059/olj.v26i1.2604.
- Macalalag, A. Z., Tan, J. R., & Francisco, R. A. (2024). Promoting social justice and equity through socio-scientific issues in science education. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 22(1), 45-63.
- Measurement of socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) and exploration of SSR as a progression of competencies | Request PDF. (2020). ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2020.1849853>
- Muhamad, I. M., Sadia, B., Siti, E. M., & Mohd, A. B. (2017). Factors Affecting Reasoning Skills on Socio Scientific Issues (SSI). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 646-652. DOI: 10.6007/IJARBSS/v7-i2/2672
- Newton, M. H., & Zeidler, D. L. (2020). Developing socioscientific perspective taking. *International Journal of Science Education*, 42(8), 1302–1319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2020.1756515>
- Nurmatova, S. & Altun, M. (2023, September 24). A Comprehensive Review of Bloom's Taxonomy Integration to Enhancing Novice EFL Educators' Pedagogical Impact. ResearchGate; AWEJ Group. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374152867_A_Comprehensive_Review_of_Bloom
- Online Business School. (2025). The role of philosophy in understanding ethics and morality. Retrieved from <https://esoftware.com/the-role-of-philosophy-in-understanding-ethics-and-morality/>.
- Owen-Smith, J. (2001). Managing Laboratory Work through Skepticism: Processes of Evaluation and Control. *American Sociological Review*, 66, 427 - 452. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Managing-Laboratory-Work-through-Skepticism%3A-of-and-Owen-Smith/1dabd1eab1da63ee036ce9ca10dd90bff2206f9a>
- Pakpahan F.H. & Saragih M. (2022, July 28). Theory Of Cognitive Development By Jean Piaget. ResearchGate; Yayasan Penelitian dan Inovasi Sumatera.

- Paraskeva-Hadjichambi, D., Hadjichambis, A. C., & Korfiatis, K. (2015). How Students' Values Are Intertwined with Decisions in a Socio-Scientific Issue. *The International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 10(3), 493–513.
<https://doi.org/10.12973/ijese.2015.256a>
- Putri, L. H., Siahaan, P., & Hernani (2020). Students' scientific reasoning and argumentative abilities through levels of inquiry models based on socio-scientific issue. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1521(4), Article 042100. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1521/4/042100>
- Rahmat, M. K., & Mohamad Nizar, N. N. (2022). The Impact of Community-Based Learning (CBL) Toward Preparing Progressive Visual Art Education (VAE) Future Trachers. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 11(4). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarped/v11-i4/15866>
- Romine, W.L., Sadler, T.D., Dauer, J.M., & Kinslow, A.T. (2020). Measurement of socio-scientific reasoning (SSR) and exploration of SSR as a progression of competencies. *International Journal of Science Education*, 42, 2981 - 3002.
 DOI:10.1080/09500693.2020.1849853
- Quintana, R. (2022). Embracing complexity in social science research. *Quality & Quantity*.
 Schiefer, M., Hofer, B. K., & Raaijmakers, S. F. (2022). Epistemic beliefs and their role in critical thinking: An integrative review.
- Sadler, T. D., & Zeidler, D. L. (2005). Patterns of informal reasoning in the context of socio-scientific decision-making. *Science Education*, 89(1), 71-93.
- Sadler, T. D., Barab, S. A., & Scott, B. (2007). What Do Students Gain by Engaging in Socioscientific Inquiry? *Research in Science Education*, 37(4), 371–391.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-006-9030-9>
- World bank climate change knowledge portal. (n.d.). Retrieved December 27, 2024, from <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/>
- Santos, L. F. (2017). The Role of Critical Thinking in Science Education. 8(20).
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320107360_The_Role_of_Critical_Thinking_in_Science_Education
- Schenk, L., Hamza, K., Arvanitis, L., Lundegård, I., Wojcik, A., & Haglund, K. (2021). Socioscientific issues in science education: An opportunity to incorporate education about risk and risk analysis?. *Risk Analysis*, 41(12), 2209-2219.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.13737>
- Siebert, J., & Siebert, M. (2023). Debiasing techniques for belief perseverance: A comprehensive study. *Journal of Cognitive Science*, 45(2), 123-135.
- Tomasello, M. (2020). The cognitive foundations of perspective-taking and its role in social cognition.
- Stender, M. Schwichow, C. Zimmerman, & H. Härtig, (2018). Making inquiry-based science learning visible: the influence of CVS and cognitive skills on content knowledge learning in guided inquiry guided inquiry, *Int. J. Sci. Educ.*, vol. 40, no. 15, pp. 1812-1831, 2018. (n.d.). <https://www.sciepub.com/reference/363607>
- Talens, J. (2016). Teaching with Socio-Scientific Issues in Physical Science: Teacher and Students' Experiences. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 5(4), 271-283. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1132589>
- Walsh, B., & Hallegatte, S. (2019). Measuring Natural Risks in the Philippines. *Openknowledge.worldbank.org*. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-8723>
- Wang, H.-H., Hong, Z.-R., She, H.-C., Smith, T. J., Fielding, J., & Lin, H.-S. (2022). The role of structured inquiry, open inquiry, and epistemological beliefs in developing secondary students' scientific and mathematical literacies. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 9 (1), 14. DOI: 10.1186/s40594-022-00329-z

- Yang, F.-Y., Bhagat, K. K., & Cheng, C.-H. (2019). Associations of epistemic beliefs in science and scientific reasoning in university students from Taiwan and India. *International Journal of Science Education*, 41(10), 1347–1365.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2019.1606960>
- Zeidler, D.L., Herman, B.C. & Sadler, T.D. New directions in socioscientific issues research. *Discip Interdiscip Sci Educ Res* 1, 11 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43031-019-0008-7>